

MEDICAL SCIENCES

THE IMPORTANCE OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES AND ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN THE FIGHT AGAINST NON-COMMUNICABLE DISEASES, ESPECIALLY PASSIVE SMOKING

**Babayev P.N.
Mamedov F.F.
Hajizade N.K.**

*Azerbaijan Medical University, Department of Public Health and Healthcare Organization,
Azerbaijan Baku city.*

Abstract

For many smokers, especially women, the fear of weight gain is the main motivation for continuing to smoke, especially given the significant impact of consuming high-calorie foods during the day. Especially in the case of psycho-emotional discomfort, the minimum consumption of fruits and vegetables consumed not only by children, but also by adults, the highest intake of fast food, sugary soft drinks, baked goods and sweets leads to eating disorders that significantly affect anthropometric indicators, especially in childhood. The diet and eating habits of schoolchildren exposed to secondhand smoke influence the development of excess body weight, which is a risk factor for obesity. AI-powered chatbot, known as QuitBot, using evidence-based strategies, helps users quit smoking.

Keywords: smoking, eating disorder, artificial intelligence

Introduction. The importance of information technologies (IT) and artificial intelligence (AI) is found not only in the education of students, but also in medicine for the treatment of various diseases, including harmful habits such as smoking and related passive smoking. Quitting smoking is usually accompanied by weight gain. With age, weight gain occurs in both smokers and non-smokers, but is more noticeable among moderate smokers. It is likely that the reason for this is the accelerated metabolic process under the influence of nicotine. For many smokers, especially women, the fear of weight gain is the main motivation for continuing to smoke, especially given the significant impact of consuming high-calorie foods during the day. Especially in the case of psycho-emotional discomfort, the minimum consumption of fruits and vegetables consumed not only by children, but also by adults, the highest intake of fast food, sugary soft drinks, baked goods and sweets leads to eating disorders that significantly affect anthropometric indicators, especially in childhood. A cutting-edge smoking cessation strategy has been developed by the Fred Hutchinson Cancer Center in Seattle, which has launched a free app with an AI-powered chatbot designed to help users quit smoking. Known as QuitBot, the app uses evidence-based strategies developed by Fred Hutch experts based on over 20 years of research. QuitBot is a comprehensive smoking cessation program consisting of 3-5-minute conversations conducted in two stages: 14 days before and 28 days after quitting. These conversations cover a wide range of topics and address users' questions, from motivation to quit and setting a quit date, to recovery from relapses and relapses, to identifying and overcoming a wide range of triggers. Users can ask QuitBot any questions about quitting, and it will respond using natural language technology developed by the researchers, guiding users through the quitting process with a specially trained artificial intelligence (AI) that interacts with them through conversations

about quitting. Unlike similar resources, QuitBot provides users with personalized support via a mobile device whenever they feel the urge. QuitBot goes a step further than other smoking cessation tools available today by offering users the ability to ask specific questions and receive personalized, scientifically proven answers, understanding users' questions about how to quit smoking and offering clinically proven answers, making the process more engaging and meaningful for the user.

Purpose. In addition to analyzing and applying innovative information technologies and artificial intelligence in the teaching process to improve the quality of education for students at the medical university, preventive measures against some diseases caused by exposure of children and their parents to tobacco smoking in the future.

Material and methods. The main physical parameters of the body are: height, weight, chest circumference. These indicators are measured to determine the physical characteristics of children exposed to and not exposed to passive smoking. By studying anthropometric indicators, it is possible to assess physical development and its compliance with age norms. This is especially important in childhood. Only fully completed questionnaires were included in the discussion. A total of 6,000 questionnaires were distributed to schoolchildren. Of these, 2,363 fully completed questionnaires contained responses from 3,895 parents – 1,885 fathers and 2,010 mothers. Since each of the 2,363 questionnaires represented one schoolchild, the survey covered 2,363 families. 687 families had children who had either graduated from secondary school or were of preschool age. Depending on the intensity of smoking, all families were divided into two groups: 818 families (tobacco-dependent) and 1,545 families (non-tobacco-dependent, i.e., control group).

Results and discussion. In recent years, new technologies such as virtual reality (VR), augmented

reality (AR), simulation, and artificial intelligence have been actively applied in medicine. Research aimed at using these technologies to model, diagnose, and treat clinical conditions is new and promising. The integration of information technologies and artificial intelligence facilitates more accurate analysis of medical data, improves the quality of diagnostics, and facilitates the development of individual treatment plans. The average values of anthropometric indicators of schoolchildren were calculated, where the reliability of their differences was clearly demonstrated. Observations were conducted in the most anthropometrically significant age groups of schoolchildren. Each anthropometric indicator—weight, height, and chest circumference—was analyzed separately and, where necessary, compared with others. We also calculated the correspondence coefficient – χ^2 , to establish a qualitative relationship between the degree of tobacco dependence, i.e. the number of cigarettes smoked per day in tobacco-dependent families and the number of schoolchildren covered by the range of our study. In our case, the calculated χ^2 value (8.58) is significantly smaller than its tabulated value (28.412) and corresponds to a probability of 0.10. This means that our null hypothesis (increasing the number of cigarettes smoked per day plays a role in the development of severe tobacco dependence) has a very significant probability—more than 0.10.

Results. Information technologies are rapidly integrating into the medical field. In addition to practical skills, doctors must be able to work with medical information systems and artificial intelligence, analyze data, use virtual simulations and telemedicine. This will help to deepen understanding of medicine in educational institutions, ensure the application of new

technologies, prepare specialists capable of effectively applying their innovations in practice.

Literature

1. Jimma B.L. Artificial intelligence in healthcare: a bibliometric analysis. *Telemat Inform Rep.* 2023; 9 (Suppl. 1): 100041. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.teler.2023.100041>.
2. Briganti G., Le Moine O. Artificial intelligence in medicine: today and tomorrow. *Front Med.* 2020; 7: 27. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmed.2020.00027>.
3. Shevchenko T. You Will Love These Examples of Using Artificial Intelligence. – Текст: электронный // letzgro.net: [сайт]. – URL: <https://letzgro.net/blog/most-awesomeexamples-of-using-artificial-intelligence-in-medicine> (дата обращения: 4.03.2020).
4. Ibragimova E.E., Yakubova E.F., Yakubova Z.A. Assessment of the impact of smoking on visceral organs and regulatory functions of the body. *Population Health and Environment.* 2018; 3 (300): 51–54/doi.org/10.35627/2219-5238/2018-300-3-51-54.
5. Kurshina M.V. The concept of health-related quality of life as a subject for scientific research in pediatrics. // *Modern trends in the development of science and technology.* 2017. No. 3. P. 28-31.
6. *Fundamentals of Nutritional Physiology: A Textbook for University Students / Editor-in-Chief A.D. Dimitrieva.* Saratov: Vuzovskoe obrazovanie, 2018. pp. 200–218. <https://doi.org/10.23682/74957>
7. Babayev P.N., Askerov Z.A. The role of passive smoking in global climate change and the negative impact of this phenomenon on the health and development of children/Scientific-practical journal named after A. Aliyev “The Medicine and Science” No. 1 35. 2024. P.62-69.